

On the appropriateness of Fire Dynamics Simulator for the road tunnel smoke control problem

Conrad Stacey¹ and Michael Beyer^{2,*}

¹Stacey Agnew Pty Ltd; conrad@staceyagnew.com

²Stacey Agnew Pty Ltd; beyer@staceyagnew.com

*Correspondence: beyer@staceyagnew.com

Abstract

NIST has made publicly available (in the FDS Validation Guide and on GitHub) Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) simulation results of the Memorial Tunnel fire tests. Those FDS results as provided by NIST can be analysed to extract a critical velocity value. That is done here, with comparison to the critical velocities observed and recorded during the Memorial Tunnel tests. The conclusion is that, for the region of interest (HRR above 30 MW), for the Memorial Tunnel cross section without the ceiling, FDS overpredicts critical velocity by 40% or so. The reasons for the overpredictions remain unknown to date, and so it is unclear how the underlying issues will affect tunnel systems different to the Memorial Tunnel. Consequently, from a practitioner's point of view, FDS cannot be relied upon to accurately assess critical or confinement velocities in road tunnels as long as the underlying problem for the discussed overpredictions is not understood and not demonstrated to be appropriately resolved. If critical velocity cannot be estimated accurately, then FDS cannot be considered a reliable tool for modelling any other deviation from the balance between forced and natural convection that is fundamental to road tunnel smoke control.

Keywords: Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS); critical velocity; confinement velocity; backlayering; tunnel safety; tunnel smoke control; validation

Background

Critical velocity is the oncoming airspeed that just prevents smoke from a tunnel fire moving against the flow. Confinement velocity is the oncoming airspeed that restricts smoke backlayering in a tunnel to a defined length. There has long been discussion about the accuracy of critical or confinement velocity prediction using CFD codes. Many design practitioners have been using Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) for this. NIST conducted FDS simulations of the Memorial Tunnel tests (using FDS version 6.8.0 and 6.9.1) and produced data files and plots of the simulation results against the recorded test results [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. A comparison of FDS results with test results of relevant Memorial Tunnel tests (longitudinal ventilation with jet fans) has been published by McGrattan and Bilson [6]. They concluded that FDS simulations of the full-scale Memorial Tunnel experiments show a tendency to over-predict the backlayering for relatively large (high heat release rate) fires under an arched ceiling, which is aligned with observations made by Beyer & Stacey [7]. McGrattan and Bilson [6] noted that the over-prediction of the backlayering implied over-prediction of the critical velocity, by as much as 25-40%. However, their critical velocity overprediction value was evaluated by using an expression that relates backlayering length at a specific velocity to a critical velocity as suggested by Li et al. [8]. That expression was developed based on small-scale fire tests and is seen to be not appropriate, for reasons established in several publications [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], and [18]. Despite the weight of evidence in those references, there are a large number of recent papers which apply scaling to small model fire tests using a "Froude" number. None of the Froude scaling-based small-scale tunnel fire test papers we have found give reference to any evidence that such scaling is valid. So, the focus here is on full-scale data only.

There are also Memorial Tunnel data with a transverse ventilation system (false ceiling still in place) but there are only eight tests with point supply and point extraction which are relevant for analysing critical velocity. Also, as concluded by Beyer et al. [19] those data are much less reliable than the data with the ceiling removed (longitudinal ventilation with jet fans).

To appropriately quantify the critical velocity prediction from the available FDS results of the relevant Memorial Tunnel experiments as published by McGrattan et al. [6], a different and more reliable methodology is provided and discussed. We analysed the data files and corresponding plots [1], [6] and [3] (upstream air/smoke temperature vs. air speed onto the fire), looking for steady periods where the smoke just started propagating upstream, to draw conclusions about the efficacy of FDS with respect to critical velocity.

No assessment is made here of the FDS model methodology applied by NIST for this problem. NIST is the developers of FDS and, for present purposes, we accept their authority on how best to apply the software to this problem. We use their FDS results [3] as documented in the validation manuals [1], [4]. These FDS input and output/results files are provided by NIST and are available on GitHub [2], [5]. We did not run or re-run the models. The simulation output data made available by NIST were used unmodified for this assessment.

We understand that the intention of the FDS simulations was to model the entire time-varying behaviour of the respective Memorial Tunnel tests. However, it is not in question that high velocities will cause smoke to move rapidly downstream and low velocities will allow it to propagate upstream. The question is about the air speed that will just stop, or limit, the backlayer growth. That cannot be judged by records of smoke backlayer moving up and down in response to changing airspeed, however comparable they look. We must look at air speeds where the backlayer is just commencing to grow from zero.

Interpreting critical velocity from the supplied traces

The backlayering was only ‘spotted’ in both the real test and FDS simulation records when it occurred at the thermocouple trees that were installed for the experiments (“Loops”). Temperature from the FDS simulations was only recorded at the same thermocouple tree locations as the full-scale Memorial Tunnel fire tests [20], [21]. Consequently, there is poor spatial resolution on both the FDS and the experimental data when the smoke is upstream of Loop 305 (4.9 m upstream of the first fire pan for 50 MW and 100 MW fire tests). The only time when the backlayering distance value is known with some precision is when the hot smoke backlayer just reaches the thermocouples at Loop 305, which is just upstream of the fire. Even then, an answer on critical velocity cannot be interpreted when airspeed is rising, due to the delay in blowing away an established backlayer.

Data for inferring critical velocity can only be taken when there is no smoke backlayer and airspeed is falling slowly. In that case, with the very short distance between the fire and Loop 305, a backlayer reaching Loop 305 will not take long to grow to that point, perhaps even from zero length. That backlayer can then be associated tightly with the velocity at that time. If the velocity is changing slowly, then there is very little uncertainty in the velocity that would give that amount of backlayering in steady state.

That means practically that there are only one or two data points relating airspeed and onset of backlayering that can legitimately be taken from any test or simulation run, and sometimes, if not sufficiently steady around critical velocity, no points can be inferred. Those velocities can then be associated with the heat release rate (HRR) in the test/simulation at the time of the record.

We analysed the FDS simulation data [1], [2], [3], [4], [5] and [6] as described above. As a check on the method, we also analysed a sample of Memorial Tunnel traces in the same way. Considering the uncertainties at the low HRR data as discussed in [14], the Memorial Tunnel test critical velocities came out as they have been published [22].

The FDS model of the Memorial Tunnel differs from the recorded tests in terms of blockage by test equipment. The blockage at Loop 305 after being ‘snapped’ to the underlying mesh was represented in the FDS model as 13.2 m² [2], but was actually recorded in the Memorial Tunnel report to be 10.2 m² [20]. This difference in Loop 305 blockage representation just upstream of the fire results in a higher local air velocity onto the fire. The critical velocity values as documented in the Memorial Tunnel report are the local air velocities at Loop 305 (1.2 times the unobstructed velocity in the tunnel obtained at

Loop 214¹ close to the entry portal). To compare the same velocities, in each case, the resulting average velocity at Loop 305 in FDS (1.28 times the unobstructed velocity in the tunnel obtained at Loop 214 close to the entry portal for consistency) is compared to the recorded critical velocity values (local velocity at Loop 305) obtained during the Memorial Tunnel tests.

Whether the velocities are called critical velocities, or confinement velocities because they may have had a few metres of backlayering, is not the point, as the same assessment methodology was applied for both the Memorial Tunnel tests and FDS traces. In fact, the numbers are very close to critical velocity as the backlayer was very short. We believe, from looking at the slight variations in upstream velocity with and without backlayering, that the velocity difference is less than 0.1 m/s. Hence, we call the assessed results critical velocities here.

As an example of the interpretation of the FDS (version 6.8.0) traces [1], [3], Figure 1 shows the FDS simulation of Memorial Tunnel Test 611. At 22.5 min into the simulation, the velocity rises to the point that all smoke is blown back past Loop 305, as shown by the ceiling temperature at that point. Shortly after that (“start of BL” line), a slight fall in velocity to just below 4.2 m/s allows the smoke to creep forward again, indicating a critical velocity of 4.2 m/s.

Figure 1. FDS simulation results for Test 611. Time-dependent tunnel air velocity at Loop 305 (approximately 5 m upstream of the 50 MW fire pan) and temperature close to the ceiling at the same loop and at Loop 306, which is located 18 m upstream of Loop 305. The fire HRR is also plotted. The yellow vertical line indicates the time when backlayering started to propagate upstream (indicated by a temperature rise at Loop 305). Traces relate to FDS version 6.8.0.

Figure 2 below shows critical velocity values of the relevant Memorial Tunnel fire tests [22], and all the critical velocities that could be assessed from the provided NIST traces for the relevant FDS runs [1], [2], [3], [4], [5] and [6] using the approach in the example above (similar figures from all 15 assessed fire tests are not provided here). At high HRR, FDS over-predicts critical velocity as shown. The plot only shows three data points for FDS at high HRR. The reason for that is again the over-prediction by FDS. Some tests never reached a high enough velocity for backlayering to be prevented in the FDS simulations.

¹ The flow rate at Loop 214 divided by the unobstructed tunnel area was used as this was demonstrated and recorded to be the most reliable velocity measurement tree for the tests with jet fans [7], [20], [21].

There were five other tests at 50 or 100 MW for which the FDS runs (at the same inputs as the real tests) never showed a critical condition, whereas the real tests did. Those tests can also be counted as evidence of over-prediction by FDS.

The analysis of the FDS 6.8.0 results has been repeated with the data from the latest FDS version 6.9.1 validation runs [4] recently made available on GitHub [5]². The orange diamonds in Figure 2 are the re-evaluated data points based on FDS version 6.9.1 results [5], [4]. One data point regarding Test 611 moved quite a bit, which is related to some anomalous behaviour in the FDS version 6.9.1 results that could not be readily explained from the available documentation. For Test 611, the HRR output by FDS 6.9.1 for some periods (especially where smoke starts propagating upstream and the critical velocity was evaluated) is not aligned with the fuel released or the test data used as input, whereas it was much better aligned using FDS 6.8.0 (see Figure 3). Under these conditions, other output parameters during those periods may also be affected and should be treated with caution. Note that the HRR was measured during the Memorial Tunnel tests, is an FDS input, and would be expected to be consistent between the two versions. The same comparison as depicted by Figure 3 is shown in Figure 4, but for Test 621A. Such issues (deviations between HRR and released fuel) were not observed for the other two re-evaluated data points (orange diamonds) and the critical velocity value stayed almost the same between FDS versions for Test 621A (increased from 4.2 m/s to 4.3 m/s). For Test 621A, the variation between versions is seen to be about the model accuracy of FDS and likely not related to any updated features / code changes. That is confirmed by the FDS release note [23], which does not address the issues raised here or by McGrattan and Bilson [6].

Figure 2. Critical velocity according to Memorial Tunnel tests as published [22] compared to the critical velocity values assessed based on the FDS validation cases by McGrattan et al. [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6].

² The latest FDS validation guide for FDS 6.10.0 [1] refers to results using FDS 6.9.1 and the validation guide for FDS 6.9.1 [4] refers to results using FDS 6.8.0.

Figure 3. Comparison of published FDS results [1], [2], [6], [3], [4], [5] for FDS version 6.8.0 according to the validation guide for FDS 6.9.1, and for the most recent version FDS 6.9.1 according to the validation guide for FDS 6.10.0. Top plots show HRR according to FDS output compared to Memorial Tunnel test data (FDS input) and the released fuel mass flow in FDS. Bottom plots show time-dependent tunnel air velocity at Loop 305 (approximately 5 m upstream of the 50 MW fire pan) and temperature close to the ceiling at the same loop and at Loop 306, which is located 18 m upstream of Loop 305. The fire HRR is also plotted. The yellow vertical line indicates the time when backlayering started to propagate upstream (indicated by a temperature rise at Loop 305). Comparison is based on Test 611.

Figure 4. Comparison of published FDS results [1], [2], [6], [3], [4], [5] for FDS version 6.8.0 according to the validation guide for FDS 6.9.1, and for the most recent version FDS 6.9.1 according to the validation guide for FDS 6.10.0. Top plots show HRR according to FDS output compared to Memorial Tunnel test data (FDS input) and the released fuel mass flow in FDS. Bottom plots show time-dependent tunnel air velocity at Loop 305 (approximately 5 m upstream of the 50 MW fire pan) and temperature close to the ceiling at the same loop and at Loop 306, which is located 18 m upstream of Loop 305. The fire HRR is also plotted. The yellow vertical line indicates the time when backlayering started to propagate upstream (indicated by a temperature rise at Loop 305). Comparison is based on Test 621A.

Conclusion

It is clear that FDS versions 6.8.0 and 6.9.1, as documented and run by NIST [1], [4], significantly overpredict critical velocity for the Memorial Tunnel cases at HRR above 30 MW. The discrepancy is around 1.2 m/s (4.2 m/s vs 3.0 m/s). Such a large discrepancy suggests that FDS versions 6.8.0 and 6.9.1 cannot be relied on for assessing critical or confinement velocity for road tunnel smoke control design. That conclusion applies until the underlying causes of the observed overpredictions are understood and shown to be appropriately resolved. If critical velocity cannot be estimated accurately, then FDS cannot be considered a reliable tool for modelling any other deviation from the balance between forced and natural convection that is fundamental to road tunnel smoke control.

Author Contributions: “Conceptualization, Conrad Stacey and Michael Beyer; methodology, Conrad Stacey and Michael Beyer; validation, Conrad Stacey and Michael Beyer; formal analysis, Michael Beyer and Conrad Stacey; resources, Conrad Stacey; data curation, Michael Beyer; writing—original draft preparation, Conrad Stacey and Michael Beyer; writing—review and editing, Conrad Stacey and Michael Beyer; funding acquisition, Conrad Stacey; investigation, Michael Beyer and Conrad Stacey. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.” Please turn to the CRediT taxonomy for the term explanation.

Funding: This research was funded partly by Stacey Agnew Pty Ltd through direct salary payments.

Data Availability Statement: Data sets generated during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Acknowledgments: We thank Matthew Bilson for providing the NIST FDS results (FDS 6.8.0) data files and Kevin McGrattan for pointing us to the newly published NIST FDS results (FDS 6.9.1) data on GitHub.

Conflicts of Interest: Dr Stacey is an owner of funding company Stacey Agnew Pty Ltd. As an author, Dr Stacey also had a strong role in the design of the study and interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, and in the decision to publish the results. There are no other intersections between funding and authorship, and there are no conflicts.

References

- [1] K. McGrattan, S. Hostikka, J. Floyd, R. McDermott, M. Vanella and E. Mueller, "NIST Special Publication 1018-3 Sixth Edition Fire Dynamics Simulator Technical Reference Guide Volume 3: Validation," National Institute of Standards and Technology, US, April 8, 2024.
- [2] K. McGrattan, "Github," 2022. [Online]. Available: https://github.com/firemodels/fds/tree/master/Validation/Memorial_Tunnel. [Accessed February 2025].
- [3] M. Bilson, *Email with NIST FDS results data files*, 13-Jan-2023.
- [4] K. McGrattan, R. McDermott, M. Vanella, E. Mueller, S. Hostikka, J. Floyd and P. Chandan, "NIST Special Publication 1018-3 Sixth Edition Fire Dynamics Simulator Technical Reference Guide Volume 3: Validation," National Institute of Standards and Technology, US, 2025.
- [5] K. McGrattan, "Github," 2025. [Online]. Available: https://github.com/firemodels/out/tree/master/Memorial_Tunnel. [Accessed March 2025].
- [6] K. McGrattan and M. Bilson, "Modeling longitudinal ventilation in tunnels using fire dynamics simulator," *Fire Safety Journal*, vol. 141, no. 103982, p. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.firesaf.2023.103982>, 2023.

- [7] M. Beyer and C. Stacey, "CFD Validation for Tunnel Smoke Control Design," in *11th International Conference Tunnel Safety and Ventilation*, Graz, <https://openlib.tugraz.at/download.php?id=6315edb636dbb&location=browse>, 9th and 10th May 2022.
- [8] Y. Li and H. Ingason, "Study of critical velocity and backlayering length in longitudinally ventilated tunnel fires," *Fire Safety Journal*, no. 45, pp. 361-370, 2010.
- [9] C. Stacey and M. Beyer, "Critical of Critical Velocity - An Industry Practitioner's Perspective," in *10th International Conference 'Tunnel Safety and Ventilation', Virtual Conference Austria*, Graz, Austria, https://www.tunnel-graz.at/assets/files/tagungsbaende/2020/13_Stacey_Beyer_Tunnel2020.pdf, 1st to 3rd of December 2020.
- [10] C. Stacey and M. Beyer, "Recorded talk on Critical of Critical Velocity - An Industry Practitioner's Perspective," in *10th International Conference 'Tunnel Safety and Ventilation', Virtual Conference Austria*, Graz, Austria, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-5rTvTnCm1M&ab_channel=StaceyAgnewPtyLtd, 1st to 3rd of December 2020.
- [11] M. Beyer, C. Stacey and A. Dix, "Critical velocity and the significance of the imminent retraction of 2020 NFPA 502's Annex D critical velocity equations part one," *Australian Tunnelling Society*, 2021, <https://australiantunnellingsociety.com.au/2021/03/11/critical-velocity-a-cautionary-note-to-practitioners/>.
- [12] Y. S. Shi, N. De Los Rios and K. Lopez, "The critical penalty," in *19th International symposium on aerodynamics, ventilation & fire in tunnels*, Brighton, UK, <https://isavft.co.uk/isavft-webshop/>, 28th to 30th of September 2022.
- [13] Y. S. Shi, I. Bowman, N. De Los Rios, N. Harvey, K. Lopez and L. Pelessone, "NFPA 502 Critical velocity calculation methodologies and dimensionless heat release rate," in *10th International symposium on tunnel safety and security*, Stavanger, <https://ri.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1805309/FULLTEXT02.pdf>, 28th April 2023.
- [14] M. Beyer, C. Stacey and G. Brenn, "A Mixed Convection Model for Estimating the Critical Velocity to Prevent Smoke Backlayering in Tunnels," *Fire Technol*, vol. 61, pp. 295-342, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10694-024-01607-8>.
- [15] M. Beyer and C. Stacey, "Confinement Velocity for Smoke in Tunnels – How to Poke a Stick at it," in *12th International Conference Tunnel Safety and Ventilation*, Graz, 2024.
- [16] P. Lin, Y. Xiong, C. Zuo and J. Shi, "Verification of Similarity of Scaling Laws in Tunnel Fires with Natural Ventilation," *Fire Technology*, vol. 57, pp. 1611-1635, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10694-020-01084-9>.
- [17] G. Grant, S. Jagger and C. Lea, "Fires in tunnels," *The Royal Society*, vol. 356, pp. 2873-2906, 1998, <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.1998.0302>.
- [18] R. Bird, W. Stewart and E. Lightfoot, *Transport Phenomena 2nd Edition*, New York: John Wiley and Sons Inc., 2002, [https://www.eng.uc.edu/~beaucag/Courses/AdvancedMaterialsThermodynamics/Books/R.%20Byron%20Bird,%20Warren%20E.%20Stewart,%20Edwin%20N.%20Lightfoot%20-%20Transport%20Phenomena,%202nd%20Edition-Wiley%20\(2001\).pdf](https://www.eng.uc.edu/~beaucag/Courses/AdvancedMaterialsThermodynamics/Books/R.%20Byron%20Bird,%20Warren%20E.%20Stewart,%20Edwin%20N.%20Lightfoot%20-%20Transport%20Phenomena,%202nd%20Edition-Wiley%20(2001).pdf).

- [19] M. Beyer, C. Stacey and G. Brenn, "Further validation of a mixed convection model of tunnel critical velocity against fullscale experimental data," *Fire Technology preprint*, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-6092275/v1>.
- [20] MTFVTP, "Memorial Tunnel Fire Ventilation Test Program - Comprehensive Test Report," Bechtel/Parsons Brinckerhoff, Boston, 1995a.
- [21] MTFVTP, "Memorial Tunnel Fire Ventilation Test Program - Memorial Tunnel Test Data Report incl. 9 discs of raw data," Bechtel/Parsons Brinckerhoff, Boston, 1995b.
- [22] G. W. Kile and J. A. Gonzalez, "The Memorial Tunnel Fire Ventilation Test Program: The Longitudinal and Natural Tests," *ASHRAE Tech Data Bulletin*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 62-74, 1997.
- [23] K. McGrattan, "Github FDS Release Notes," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/firemodels/fds/wiki/FDS-Release-Notes>.